

Table continued

Entry, culture	Whiteheads (%)
<i>Scented tall</i>	
HBC19	43.9
HBC143	42.9
Pak Basmati	41.9
HBC46	38.3
Basmati 370	35.1
HBC28	32.1
<i>New lines</i>	
IET12606	50.8
IET12604	37.3
Basmati No. 2	25.3
IET12602	22.7
IET12601	21.6
IET12607	19.3
IET12605	15.7
IET12608	12.0
IET12603	8.6
IET12609	6.7

table). None of the scented tall entries were promising.

New entries IET12609, IET12603, and IET12608 showed promise for resistance to the pest. □

Effects of whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) *Sogatella furcifera* on rice varieties in the greenhouse

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We screened 42 rice varieties and lines against WBPH using the seedling bulk test. Test lines were sown 20 seeds/row in 10-cm-long rows in 40- × 30- × 5-cm iron seedboxes filled with 3 cm of fine soil, in a randomized complete design with three replications.

Seedlings were infested 7 d after sowing with second- to third-instar WBPH nymphs at 5 nymphs/seedling. Plant damage was assessed when all plants of susceptible check TN1 had died.

Two lines showed moderate resistance to WBPH with damage score 3, and 21 lines were moderately susceptible with damage score 5 (see table). □

Reaction of rice varieties to WBPH under greenhouse conditions in 1991 wet season.

Variety	Damage score ^a
A21	3
IR50404-57-2-2-3	3
IR32843-92	5
IR49517-32	5
IR50404-47	5
OM746-13	5
IR44595-70	5
IR44592-62	5
OM44-5	5
OM201	5
OM723-11E	5
IR64	5
OM723-7	5
OM723-11M	5
IR70	5
OM742-15	5
IR52280-117-1-1-3	5
IR42W-211-1-2-2-3	5
IR53970-100-3-3-2	5
A20	5
A8	5
24A	5
Ptb 33 (resistant check)	3
TN1 (susceptible check)	9

^a By the Standard evaluation system for rice.

Pest resistance—other pests

Assessment of rice resistance and susceptibility to stem nematode *Ditylenchus angustus*

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We examined ways to assess rice resistance and susceptibility to stem nematode *D. angustus*, the cause of ufra. We screened selections, most of which were identified through the International Rice Ufra Screening Set (1985-89), in successive glasshouse trials against an isolate of *D. angustus* from Haugiang, Vietnam.

Inoculum consisting of 300 *D. angustus* nematodes and eggs was placed in water 10-12 d after sowing (10 cm deep) and confined close to each seedling, using a 6-mm-diam drinking straw. The straw was removed per 7 d. Symptom development was monitored daily and nematodes/plant

Diagrammatic representation of symptoms of *D. angustus*: A = susceptible, with severity rated 0-16, and B = resistant.

were counted 28 d after inoculation (DAI). This method was reliable, giving 100% infection of the susceptible check NC492 with 1,047 *D. angustus*/plant (mean of 68 plants, standard error of mean = 74).

Symptoms on the most recent leaf were classified every 7 d as resistant (incompatible) or susceptible (compatible). Severity of susceptible responses was scored on a scale of 0-16 (see fig., A). Some resistant seedlings exhibited

Proportion of plants of Rayada 16-06 showing resistant and susceptible symptoms, 28 d after inoculation with *D. angustus*.

Host response	Plants (%)	<i>D. angustus</i>	
		Mean no./plant	Range/plant
Resistant-immune	13	0	0
Resistant-hypersensitive	49	2	0-13
Susceptible	38	46	6-572

a hypersensitive response that was visible 5 DAI. Resistance response was varied: leaves showed discrete, small white patches bordered by a yellowish halo, sometimes over the entire leaf surface, or the leaf midrib became yellowish, either in discrete areas or along its length (see fig., B). In what appears to be a strong resistant response, a length of the emerging leaf was completely chlorotic below a green tip, with the leaf often folding in the chlorotic region.

This response differs markedly from the well-described susceptible reaction.

The necrosis of infected resistant tissue is rapid, whereas it is slower in the susceptible response and usually follows a secondary infection by fungi.

The response was observed in some seedlings of Bazail 65, CNL 319, Karkati 161, Rayada 16-02, Rayada 16-03, and Rayada 16-06 to Rayada 16-09. We screened 100 seedlings of Rayada 16-06 to examine interplant variation. We observed host responses (see table). Within a rice line, or between lines and cultivars, the type of response and level of susceptibility could be accurately

judged from visual symptoms. Numerical scores of susceptible symptom severity at 28 DAI were linearly related to numbers of *D. angustus*/ plant (within Rayada 16-06, correlation coefficient $r = 0.70$, $P < 0.001$; between lines and cultivars, $r = 0.74$, $P < 0.001$).

Results indicate that host variation has a strong genetic component and that single plants can be qualitatively assessed. Differences in the level of susceptibility in compatible responses depend on the reproduction rate of *D. angustus* which has an environmental component. □

Irrigated germplasm improvement—irrigated

Yield performance of some new rice hybrids in Indonesia

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We compared 7 IRRI rice hybrids and 13 Indonesian hybrids with IR64 and

Way-Seputih in yield trials during the 1990-91 wet season (WS) in Sukamandi and Kuningan. Single seedlings were transplanted at 20- × 20-cm spacing in 3- × 5-m² plots with three replications. Plots were fertilized with 135-50-50 kg NPK/ha.

IR64616 H, IR64618 H, IR64610 H, and IR62829 A/IR54 yielded more than Way-Seputih, although all the rice

hybrids yielded significantly less than best check IR64 at Sukamandi. The hybrids had lower 1,000-grain weights and less filled grains/panicle than IR64.

All test entries at Sukamandi outperformed those at Kuningan. IR64 and Way-Seputih, however, still yielded significantly more than any of the hybrids (see table). □

Grain yield, maturity, 1000-grain weight, filled grains per panicle, panicle number per hill, unfilled grains per panicle, and plant height of some rice hybrids. Sukamandi (S) and Kuningan (K), Indonesia, 1990-91 WS.

Hybrid or check	Yield (t/ha)		Maturity (d)		1000-grain weight (g)		Filled grains/panicle (no.)		Unfilled grains/panicle (no.)		Panicles/hill		Plant height (cm)	
	S	K	S	K	S	K	S	K	S	K	S	K	S	K
IR64 (check)	6.8	4.7	116	133	30.20	26.97	100	61	15	31	14	11	116	84
IR64616 H	6.3	3.0	114	132	26.57	23.80	98	47	52	64	14	12	102	81
IR64618	5.2	3.6	112	127	24.90	22.03	97	69	27	33	14	13	106	84
IR64610H	4.9	3.7	111	130	24.57	22.06	83	61	31	51	16	14	101	83
IR62829 A/IR54	4.8	4.0	116	127	26.70	23.03	78	46	50	54	15	13	107	84
Way-Seputih (check)	4.7	4.9	130	133	31.30	27.57	100	91	23	35	16	11	125	85
IR64611 H	4.6	3.9	112	129	25.73	22.90	72	57	57	47	17	12	113	84
IR62829 A/M666	4.4	4.1	116	127	26.20	23.17	86	48	61	42	20	14	104	83
IR62829 A/IR64	4.4	3.3	118	120	26.17	22.83	101	46	65	44	14	15	109	82
IR62829 A/Cimanuk	4.2	3.2	115	127	25.63	21.70	88	47	46	48	15	12	96	84
IR54752 A/M66b	4.2	2.1	120	129	28.83	25.40	139	41	44	53	15	12	135	88
V20 A/M66b	4.2	2.3	104	122	27.73	24.17	87	56	28	38	14	10	108	82
IR64617 H	3.8	-	120	-	25.83	-	77	-	74	-	14	-	117	-
V20 A/IR64	3.8	2.5	104	122	28.63	23.00	90	49	32	46	13	12	106	77
IR6461514	3.5	1.7	117	132	27.03	24.06	82	49	76	37	11	11	113	83
IR54752 A/IR54	3.5	1.8	122	129	27.67	26.17	97	50	40	67	15	12	135	92
IR54752 A/IR64	3.3	1.4	121	127	29.17	26.63	108	50	50	52	19	11	134	87
V20 A/IR54	3.3	2.0	103	122	27.70	22.53	109	68	32	36	12	12	111	83
V20 A/Cimanuk	2.6	2.0	104	122	27.90	22.80	100	52	35	40	12	11	102	77
IR54752 A/Sadang	2.6	1.2	121	127	30.20	26.20	99	44	50	84	18	11	146	87
IR54752 A/Cimanuk	2.6	1.5	120	127	29.33	25.60	110	41	45	66	18	11	135	93
IR58025 A/IR54742	2.5	3.6	130	133	31.13	26.93	118	65	68	43	17	12	134	88
LSD 0.05	1.3	0.7	3.0	2.0	1.17	0.54	31.5	16.7	22.3	15.1	4.9	1.3	7.9	3.8
CV (%)	20.1	17.1	1.7	1.2	2.61	1.37	20.6	19.6	29.9	18.8	20.6	6.6	4.2	2.8